

DEVELOPING LISTENING COMPREHENSION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

Barno Djumanova

English teacher of Languages department, Yangi Asr university

Fayziyeva Shahrizoda,

1st year student of English philology, Yangi Asr university

E-mail: yangiasruniversiteti@gmail.com

Annotation: Listening is a fundamental skill in language learning, and its development is crucial for effective communication. This article explores various methods for improving listening comprehension, focusing on theoretical aspects and practical activities. Additionally, it examines traditional and modern teaching approaches to listening skills in ELT.

Key Words: Listening comprehension, ELT, language acquisition, audio-lingual method, listening activities, teaching methodologies.

Listening is one of the four core language skills, along with speaking, reading, and writing. It plays a vital role in understanding and communicating effectively in any language. In English language teaching (ELT), listening comprehension is often

considered one of the most challenging aspects for learners. Importance of Listening in Language Learning: Listening is the primary channel through which language learners acquire new vocabulary, pronunciation, and sentence structures. Effective listening improves speaking skills and overall language proficiency. Without proper listening skills, communication can be hindered, leading to misunderstandings. What is Listening? Listening is the ability to accurately receive and interpret messages in the communication process. It is an active skill that requires concentration, background knowledge, and the ability to distinguish relevant information from distractions. **Listening skills** refer to a person's ability to actively receive, interpret, and respond to spoken information effectively. These skills are crucial for communication and learning. Strong listening skills help in understanding messages accurately, avoiding misunderstandings, and engaging in meaningful conversations. [7,23]. Some scholars provided types of listening skills:

Active Listening – Fully concentrating, understanding, and responding thoughtfully.

Critical Listening – Evaluating and analyzing the message for deeper understanding.

Empathetic Listening – Understanding the speaker's emotions and perspective.

Selective Listening – Focusing on specific parts of the message while ignoring distractions.

Appreciative Listening – Enjoying and appreciating sounds, such as music or storytelling.

How Was Listening Skill Taught? Listening was traditionally taught using rote memorization, repetition, and teacher-centered methods. Students primarily listened to recorded dialogues and repeated them to develop pronunciation and comprehension skills. However, these methods often lacked interactive elements, making it challenging for learners to apply listening skills in real-life situations. The audio-lingual method is another teaching approach that has been initially focused on speaking proficiency.

An urgent need to review and restructure the learning process can be explained historically. The start of World War II made it more crucial than ever for Americans to learn the languages of both their enemies and friends. Consequently, fragments of the Direct Method were taken to create and reinforce this new approach, the “Army Method,” which eventually became known as the Audiolingual Method in the 1950s. The main focus of the method was to shape the habit of using certain structures, patterns and verbs through repetition and drilling, and general extensive exposure to the examples that needed to be recreated. Audio-Lingual Method: The Audio-Lingual Method (ALM) was a widely used approach in the mid-20th century. It was based on behaviorist theories, emphasizing repetition, drills, and pattern practice. In ALM, students listened to dialogues, repeated phrases, and engaged in structured exercises to reinforce their listening and speaking skills. Although this method helped develop pronunciation and fluency, it lacked contextual understanding and critical thinking engagement.

How is Listening Taught Nowadays? Today, listening is taught using interactive and communicative approaches. Teachers incorporate real-life audio materials, technology, and engaging activities to enhance comprehension skills. Some modern techniques include. The listening test is designed to test how well you understand spoken English.

So, the most obvious way to improve your listening skills is to listen to lots of English being spoken. But what should you listen to? You’ll find everything you need for free online. Whether you’ve can spare just a few

minutes to listen or have an hour of study time planned, there’s a wealth of material that you can access in seconds. Listen to a range of things. The test will include two monologues (one person speaking) and two conversations, so you must practice listening to both. [8,34]

-Online News Channels are ideal because news broadcasts contain a good mix of reports and conversations. For all parts of the IELTS exam, I recommend BBC News as the best news channel to tune in to.

However, for the Listening test, listen to the news from a range of English speaking countries (UK, Ireland, US, Canada, New Zealand, Australia and South Africa) so you get used to understanding different accents.

-Podcasts are also an excellent resource. They can last for as little as 2 minutes or go on for an hour or more. They also cover a vast range of topics so you’ll easily find something interesting to listen to in the time you have available.

-**TED Talks** are equally as useful. These are online lectures, often very short, and are perfect for practicing listening to monologues. Again, the range of topics is huge.

-**Online Radio** is one of the best sources for interviews so, tune in to a good station when you want to practice listening to conversations.

• If you listen to something every day, ideally for at least 10-15 minutes, your listening skills will gradually improve. [8,13];

Now let's look at some more activities on how to improve students' listening skills.

Authentic Materials: Podcasts, interviews, TED Talks, and movies expose students to real spoken English with diverse accents and contexts. **Task-Based Learning:** Students engage in listening tasks that require them to extract key information, summarize, and respond.

Interactive Applications: Digital tools and online platforms provide instant feedback and self-paced learning opportunities.

In teaching process teachers should use some various activities [9,2] and in the following there are some of them:

1. *Dictation Exercises* - Students listen to a passage and write down what they hear.

This improves attention to detail, spelling, and comprehension. 2. *Gap-2.Fill Listening* -Learners listen to a conversation or a lecture and fill in missing words in a transcript. This activity enhances vocabulary retention and understanding of context.

3. *Interactive Listening Games* - Role-playing and question-answer activities encourage students to actively engage in listening and responding appropriately, making learning more interactive and enjoyable. [10,5]

By the way of conclusion, developing listening comprehension is essential for language learners, as it directly impacts their ability to communicate effectively. By incorporating modern teaching methods and engaging activities, teachers can significantly improve students' listening skills. Utilizing diverse listening materials and interactive tasks can lead to better comprehension and overall language proficiency.

Reference list

1. <https://www.indeed.com/careeradvice/career-development/how-to-improvelistening-skills>
2. <https://learnenglish.britishcouncil.org/skills/listenin g>
3. <https://blogs.iadb.org/educacion/en/listening-skills/>
4. https://listenwise.com/improve_listening_compre nsion/
5. <https://grade-university.com/blog/the-history-ofthe-method-the-audio-lingualmethod>
6. https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Audiolingual_method
7. Hosam Elmetaher . Nanzan University, Nagoya, Aichi, Japan MEXTESOL Journal,

Developing English Listening Skills: Can Active Learning Help?Vol. 45, No. 3, 2021

8.Nodira Rashidova, Ziyatova Zamira, Otabayev Muzaffar. DEVELOPING LISTENING COMPREHENSION IN ELT .European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements (EJHEA) Vol. 2 No. 6, 2021 ISSN: 2660-5589 28 |

9. B1 Preliminary for Schools Developing listening skills for Cambridge English Qualifications: A guide for teachers

10.DEVELOPMENT OF READING, WRITING, LISTENING, SPEAKING SKILLS IN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

11.<https://www.ieltsjacky.com/how-to-improve-ieltslistening.html>